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Physico-Chemical Profile of the Poovar Estuary: An Ecological and Tourism Hotspot in South Kerala, India

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Abstract

Water is the basis of life and the environment. If the water is not utilized sustainably, it will lead to scarcity and cause destruction. Along with the water, its quality should also be maintained. The present study was carried out to analyse the water quality of Poovar Estuary, Thiruvananthapuram, Kerala. Poovar Estuary is a well-known tourist destination, which is popular for floating resorts and boating in the mangrove forest. The present study focused on physico-chemical analysis such as temperature, pH, conductivity, salinity, total dissolved solids, alkalinity, acidity, carbon dioxide, hardness, sodium, potassium, dissolved oxygen, biochemical oxygen demand, and MPN (Most Probable Number) based on APHA (1992). Fifteen samples in all were taken at various locations along the estuary. The study region has significant quantities of potassium and sodium. The MPN is very high at most sampling sites, because of the extremely high level of *E. coli* present, it is not suitable for household consumption. To prevent health issues, some measures must be taken to lower the coliforms in the water.

Keywords: Water quality; Poovar estuary; MPN; Anthropogenic activities; Pollution control; Sustainable management

Introduction

Water is an indispensable resource that sustains life and ecosystems on Earth, playing a central role in environmental processes and human well-being. It regulates climate, supports biodiversity, and underpins agriculture, industry, and domestic needs (Gleick, 1993; Allan, 2001). The hydrological cycle, encompassing evaporation, condensation, precipitation, infiltration, and runoff, ensures the circulation and redistribution of water across ecosystems, driven by solar energy and gravity (Shiklomanov, 1993; Maidment, 1993). Water exists in multiple states—liquid, solid, and vapor—and its continuous cycling influences landscape formation through processes of erosion, dissolution, and deposition (Postel and Carpenter, 1997). Biologically, water forms the primary component of life, constituting up to 90–95% of microbial biomass, 80–90% of herbaceous plants, and 50–70% of woody plants (Carpenter et al., 1998; Boyd, 2019). Globally, about 97.5% of Earth's water is saline, leaving only 2.5% as freshwater. Of this, 68.7% is stored in glaciers and ice caps, 30.1% in groundwater, and merely 1.2% in rivers, lakes, and wetlands (Gleick, 1998; UNEP, 2018). These freshwater resources form the backbone of human societies, sustaining agriculture, industries, energy production, and domestic supply (FAO, 2021; UNESCO, 2009). Aquatic ecosystems such as rivers, lakes, wetlands, and estuaries are biodiversity hotspots, providing ecosystem services including nutrient cycling, flood regulation, water purification, and carbon sequestration (MEA, 2005; Chapin et al., 2009). However, freshwater distribution is spatially and temporally uneven, creating challenges in availability and accessibility across regions (Vörösmarty et al., 2000; Ashiq, 2012).

Water resources are increasingly under pressure due to anthropogenic activities such as rapid urbanization, deforestation, industrialization, and agricultural intensification (Kumar, 2018;

Thomas, 2012). These activities alter hydrological regimes, degrade habitats, and contribute to water pollution, thereby reducing the availability of clean water for both human and ecological needs (UN Water, 2020; WHO, 2018). Climate change further exacerbates water-related risks through altered rainfall patterns, sea-level rise, glacial melt, and extreme events such as floods and droughts (IPCC, 2014; UNEP, 2021). Sustainable management of water thus requires integrated approaches that combine hydrology, ecology, engineering, and policy interventions (Postel, 1996; Gleick, 2003).

In India, water resources are critical to socio-economic development, with rivers and Himalayan snow cover supporting agriculture, hydropower, industry, and domestic consumption (Nihal, 2012; Kumar et al., 2015). Kerala, often termed "God's Own Country," is uniquely blessed with a dense network of rivers such as the Periyar, Pamba, and Bharathapuzha, originating from the Western Ghats and feeding agriculture, power generation, and domestic supply (Kerala State Planning Board, 2020). These waters also support fisheries, biodiversity, tourism, and cultural traditions (Sreedharan and Karthikeyan, 2012). However, increasing population, industrial growth, agricultural runoff, and untreated sewage discharge threaten water quality, while seasonal and spatial variability in rainfall complicates water availability (Kerala State Pollution Control Board, 2021; Nair, 2010).

Water use spans multiple dimensions. Domestically, it is essential for drinking, sanitation, and hygiene, which are key to public health (WHO/UNICEF, 2019). Agriculturally, irrigation ensures food security and underpins rural livelihoods (FAO, 2021). Industrially, water is indispensable for cooling, processing, cleaning, and energy production (UNIDO, 2019). Beyond human uses, water sustains biodiversity, regulates climate, and maintains ecological balance (UNEP, 2020). Mismanagement, however, has led to water scarcity, falling groundwater levels, and pollution, threatening long-term sustainability (Vörösmarty et al., 2000; UNEP, 2018).

A particularly critical concern is water pollution, which arises from industrial effluents, agricultural runoff, plastic waste, heavy metals, sewage, and pathogens (UN Water, 2020; Bhatia et al., 2013). Such contamination not only disrupts aquatic ecosystems and biodiversity but also poses direct health risks to humans through drinking water and food chains (WHO, 2018). Effective water quality management requires monitoring, watershed protection, wastewater treatment, pollution prevention, and strong regulatory enforcement (USEPA, 2020; Boyd, 2019). In Kerala, rapid urbanization, tourism, and poor waste management exacerbate water quality deterioration, necessitating urgent conservation and policy measures (Kerala State Pollution Control Board, 2021; Kumar, 2018).

Special ecosystems such as estuaries highlight the ecological complexity of water systems. Estuaries, where rivers meet the sea, are nutrient-rich transitional zones supporting high biodiversity, nursery habitats, and ecosystem services such as coastal protection and fisheries (Pritchard, 1967; NOAA, 2020). Indian estuaries, particularly along the western coast, are ecologically and economically significant, with major systems such as the Ganges, Godavari, Krishna, and Vembanad sustaining millions of livelihoods (Potter et al., 2010; Nair, 2010). The Poovar Estuary in Kerala is a prime example, where the Neyyar River meets the Arabian Sea, creating habitats such as mangroves and mudflats that support diverse flora and fauna but face threats from tourism and pollution (Kumar et al., 2015; Sreedharan & Karthikeyan, 2012). Water is not merely a physical resource but an ecological and socio-economic foundation. Its availability, quality, and sustainable management determine the resilience of ecosystems and societies in the face of global change. Effective stewardship of water resources—balancing human demands with ecosystem needs—remains one of the most pressing challenges of the 21st century.

The objectives of the present study are to analyze the water quality characteristics of the study area, to assess the impacts of anthropogenic activities on the health status of the region, and to suggest conservation strategies for the sustainable management of the area under investigation.

Study area

The Poovar Estuary, located in the Thiruvananthapuram district of Kerala, India (8°19'3"N, 77°4'17"E), is a unique ecosystem formed at the confluence of the Neyyar River and the Arabian Sea. This estuarine system is characterized by tidal influences and the mixing of freshwater and seawater, creating a dynamic and ever-changing environment shaped by riverine sediment deposition and coastal tidal movements. Rich in mangroves and aquatic biodiversity, the estuary plays a vital role in maintaining regional ecological balance by supporting nutrient cycling, local

fisheries, and acting as a natural barrier against coastal erosion. The mangrove forests, which harbor diverse flora and fauna, also feature unique natural formations such as the Anaconda Cave. In addition to its ecological significance, Poovar is a hub of socio-economic activity, with boating and fishing sustaining local livelihoods and tourism thriving through attractions such as floating resorts and numerous establishments along the estuarine banks.

Sampling and analysis

For the physico-chemical assessment of the Poovar Estuary, a preliminary survey was conducted, and water sampling was carried out on June, 2024, between 7:00 and 10:00. A total of 15 samples were collected from different locations at intervals of 1–1.5 km, with each sample taken from the midstream. Sterile bottles were rinsed thrice with estuarine water prior to sampling, and the collected samples were stored in insulated containers with ice to preserve their quality. Physical parameters such as temperature, colour, and odour were recorded on-site. For BOD and DO analysis, water was collected in 250 ml Niskin and Scotty bottles, ensuring the absence of air bubbles, and DO samples were fixed immediately with manganese sulphate and alkaline potassium iodide solutions. For bacteriological analysis, samples for the Most Probable Number (MPN) method were collected separately in pre-sterilized 100 ml dark bottles, kept at 4°C, and transported under controlled conditions until analysis.

In the laboratory, water quality parameters were analyzed following standard APHA (1992) procedures. These included the estimation of temperature, pH, total dissolved solids, free carbon dioxide, conductivity, alkalinity, acidity, hardness, salinity, dissolved oxygen, and biochemical oxygen demand. Trace elements such as sodium and potassium were quantified using flame photometry, while bacteriological quality was determined using the multiple tube MPN method. Together, these analyses provided a comprehensive understanding of the physico-chemical and microbiological status of the estuarine waters.

Results and discussion

The physicochemical parameters of water quality across the sampled sites indicate spatial variability influenced by freshwater inflows, seawater mixing, and anthropogenic disturbances. Temperature ranged from 27°C at S₄, S₆, S₉, and S₁₀ to a maximum of 30°C at S₁, with a mean of 28.20°C (SD = 0.94). Temperature strongly influenced other parameters, showing positive correlations with pH, electrical conductivity (EC), total dissolved solids (TDS), hardness, potassium, dissolved oxygen (DO), and biochemical oxygen demand (BOD), while being negatively associated with carbon dioxide, acidity, salinity, alkalinity, and sodium. These findings are consistent with earlier studies that linked higher water temperatures with increased metabolic rates of aquatic organisms, reduced oxygen solubility, and enhanced algal bloom formation (Smith et al., 1999; Wetzel, 2001).

The pH of water samples varied between 7.17 at S₁₂ and 8.45 at S₂ (mean = 7.76; SD = 0.31). Sites with higher pH values coincided with sea–river mixing zones, suggesting seawater intrusion and reduced freshwater input as possible causes (Pritchard, 1956; Gordon et al., 1995). The pH exhibited positive associations with salinity, EC, and sodium, while being negatively correlated with acidity and hardness. Deviations from the standard limit (6.5–8.5) were observed at three sites, and such fluctuations can significantly influence solubility and toxicity of metals, thus impacting aquatic health (Hood, 2003; EPA, 2018). Electrical conductivity values were highest at S₈ (11.84 mg/L) and lowest at S₁₅ (2.76 mg/L), with a mean of 7.45 mg/L (SD = 3.56). Higher EC values near seawater mixing zones indicated elevated dissolved ions, while lower values in freshwater-dominated sites reflected dilution. Elevated EC is a recognized indicator of salinization and pollution from runoffs, often affecting nutrient availability and ecological balance (Boyd, 2015; APHA, 2012; Rizzo et al., 2012). Similarly, salinity levels peaked at S₈ (6.23 ppt) and were lowest at S₁₅ (1.42 ppt), with a mean of 4.08 ppt (SD = 1.97). Salinity variations followed a similar spatial pattern to EC, being higher near marine influence. Excessive salinity can disrupt freshwater biodiversity and reduce ecosystem stability (Brock et al., 2010; Tang & Li, 2010).

TDS values ranged between 1.88 ppm at S₁₂ and 9.57 ppm at S₈ (mean = 5.99 ppm; SD = 1.97). High TDS values corresponded with salinity and EC trends, indicating strong seawater intrusion and pollutant load. Elevated TDS is associated with reduced water clarity, oxygen depletion, and physiological stress in aquatic organisms (Larsen & Wark, 2012; Kumar et al., 2016). Conversely, very low TDS suggests poor nutrient availability for aquatic communities (WHO, 2006; Manning, 2017).

Alkalinity levels varied between 50 mg/L at S15 and 120 mg/L at S10 (mean = 89.33 mg/L; SD = 19.71), reflecting buffering capacity contributed by mixing processes and land geology (Stumm & Morgan, 1996). Moderate alkalinity is generally beneficial for stabilizing pH, but low levels could increase vulnerability to acidification (Kimmel et al., 1990). Acidity values were highest at S9 (57.5 mg/L) and lowest at S1 and S11 (7.5 mg/L), with a mean of 17.66 mg/L (SD = 13.44). Elevated acidity at S9 may be attributed to decomposition and respiration activities producing organic acids (Gordon et al., 1996). Such conditions increase metal solubility and toxicity (Schofield et al., 1985; Driscoll et al., 2001).

Sl. No.	Parameters	Sample Locations														
		1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15
1	Temp. (°C)	30	29	28	27	29	27	28	29	27	27	29	28	28	28	29
2	pH	7.90	8.45	8.10	7.66	7.85	7.88	8.20	7.69	7.51	7.56	7.62	7.17	7.67	7.74	7.58
3	EC (µS/cm)	9.17	9.75	9.18	9.97	10.19	10.25	11.44	11.84	9.55	4.79	5.12	2.34	3.01	2.47	2.76
4	Salinity	5.01	5.32	5.01	5.57	5.54	5.85	6.22	6.04	5.72	2.50	2.64	1.18	2.07	1.11	1.42
5	TDS	7.29	7.70	7.32	8.13	8.13	8.41	8.90	9.56	7.54	3.82	4.10	1.88	3.20	1.70	2.22
6	Alkalinity (mg/L)	95	85	75	80	95	100	100	95	115	120	110	70	60	90	50
7	Acidity (mg/L)	7.5	10	12.5	12.5	15	20	17.5	27.5	57.5	35	7.5	12.5	10	12.5	7.5
8	CO ₂ (mg/L)	11	8.8	19.8	33	26.4	15.4	39.6	15.4	41.8	22	4.4	8.8	11	8.8	11
9	Hardness (mg/L)	1.4	1.5	1.8	1.2	1.7	0.8	1.2	1.3	1.7	1.5	1.2	1.5	1.3	1.6	1.7
10	Na (mg/L)	18.62	16.67	18.84	20.04	19.66	18.92	20.45	21.67	11.26	09.12	07.55	04.53	06.88	03.35	04.40
11	K (mg/L)	15.27	14.01	17.15	16.07	12.21	14.72	13.24	10.81	11.91	9.48	10.21	8.94	11.47	16.01	15.71
12	DO	4.2	3.8	1.1	1.9	3.1	4.02	2.87	2.06	2.78	2.12	1.98	2.56	1.5	1.27	1.89
13	BOD	1.07	1.78	0.91	0.2	1.8	0.12	1.09	0.94	1.72	1.07	0.87	1.23	0.81	0.56	1.21
14	MPN	1600	1600	1600	1600	1600	1600	1600	1600	1600	1600	1600	1600	1600	1600	1600

Table 1. Water quality results

Carbon dioxide levels varied widely, from 4.4 mg/L at S11 to 41.5 mg/L at S9 (mean = 18.42 mg/L; SD = 11.78). CO₂ dynamics were linked to turbulence, carbon cycling, and biological activity. Excess CO₂ promotes acidification and reduces the survival of calcifying organisms (Caldeira & Wickett, 2003; Hoegh-Guldberg et al., 2007). Hardness values remained relatively low, ranging between 0.8 mg/L at S6 and 1.8 mg/L at S3 (mean = 1.42 mg/L; SD = 0.26). Such variation reflects sediment dissolution and anthropogenic influences like agricultural runoff (Meybeck, 1988; Nixon, 1995). While moderate hardness provides essential minerals, extreme values impair ecological and domestic utility (Dodds, 2002; Niemann et al., 2004).

Table 2. Discriptive statistics

Sl.No.	DESCRIPTIVE STATISTICS				
		Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
1	Temperature	27.00	30.00	28.2000	0.94112
2	pH	7.17	8.45	7.7653	.30926
3	Conductivity	2.34	11.84	7.4553	3.56238
4	Salinity	1.11	6.22	4.0800	1.97808
5	TDS	1.70	9.56	5.9933	2.81054
6	Alkalinity	50.00	120.00	89.3333	19.71825
7	Acidity	7.50	57.50	17.6667	13.44522
8	CO ₂	4.40	41.80	18.4800	11.78299
9	Hardness	.80	1.80	1.4267	0.26583
10	Sodium	335.00	2126.00	1383.6667	686.88465
11	Potassium	89.40	171.50	131.4733	26.39295
12	DO	1.10	4.20	2.4767	0.97375
13	BOD	.12	1.80	1.0253	0.50319
	MPN	1600.00	1600.00	1600.0000	0.00000

Sodium concentrations showed extreme variability, ranging from 453 mg/L at S12 to 2167 mg/L at S8 (mean = 138.66 mg/L; SD = 686.88). High sodium values near seawater intrusion sites point to marine influence, while anthropogenic inputs such as agriculture may also contribute (Smith and Karr, 1981). Excess sodium alters water taste and is linked to health concerns such as hypertension (Falk et al., 2002; Choi et al., 2013). Potassium levels were between 89.2 mg/L at S12 and 160.1 mg/L at S14 (mean = 131.47 mg/L; SD = 26.39), likely originating from agricultural runoff, wastewater discharge, and soil–rock interactions (Meybeck, 1988; Nixon, 1995). Elevated potassium is linked to eutrophication and associated oxygen depletion (Gilbert et al., 2011).

Table 3. Pearson Corrélation Table

	Temp	pH	EC	Salinity	TDS	Alkalinity	Acidity	CO ₂	Hardness	Na	K	DO	BOD
Temperature	1												
pH	.291	1											
EC	.023	.558*	1										
Salinity	-.035	.544*	.993**	1									
TDS	.011	.544*	.996**	.994**	1								
Alkalinity	-.223	.053	.405	.394	.375	1							
Acidity	-.539*	-.262	.268	.304	.259	.600*	1						
CO ₂	-.513	.094	.555*	.594*	.544*	.361	.619*	1					
Hardness	.206	-.016	-.250	-.259	-.284	-.214	.139	.062	1				
Na	-.001	.528*	.985**	.985**	.988**	.341	.240	.571*	-.222	1			
K	.054	.497	.217	.224	.204	-.344	-.342	.061	.105	.255	1		
DO	.232	.300	.481	.497	.473	.323	.057	.058	-.341	.455	-.023	1	
BOD	.385	.170	.082	.083	.056	.087	.261	.145	.648**	.046	-.323	.264	1

DO concentrations were generally low, with a maximum of 4.2 mg/L at S1 and minimum of 1.1 mg/L at S3 (mean = 2.47 mg/L; SD = 0.97). Low DO values suggest organic matter loading, algal blooms, and reduced water mixing, all of which threaten aquatic life (Wetzel, 2001; Diaz and Rosenberg, 2008). Correspondingly, BOD values were low, ranging from 0.91 mg/L at S3 to 1.78 mg/L at S2 (mean = 1.03 mg/L; SD = 0.50), suggesting moderate organic pollution. High BOD levels are typically linked to wastewater discharge and organic enrichment (Lazarova et al., 2000; APHA, 2012).

The Most Probable Number (MPN) analysis revealed fecal coliform concentrations exceeding 1600 in all the sites, reflecting significant microbial contamination from improper sewage disposal and leaching (Payment et al., 2000). High coliform levels elevate the risk of gastrointestinal diseases and contribute to eutrophication, ultimately deteriorating ecosystem quality (Gordon et al., 2008). Overall, these results underscore the influence of both natural processes (seawater–freshwater mixing, sediment dissolution) and anthropogenic activities (agriculture, sewage, industrial discharges) on water quality. While most parameters fell within acceptable limits, elevated salinity, sodium, TDS, and microbial load highlight ecological stressors that require integrated management strategies.

Table 4. Analysis of variance (ANOVA) table

		ANOVA				
		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
pH	Between Groups	.121	3	.040	.365	.780
	Within Groups	1.218	11	.111		
	Total	1.339	14			
Conductivity	Between Groups	25.307	3	8.436	.609	.623
	Within Groups	152.361	11	13.851		
	Total	177.668	14			
Salinity	Between Groups	8.310	3	2.770	.656	.596
	Within Groups	46.469	11	4.224		
	Total	54.779	14			
TDS	Between Groups	15.851	3	5.284	.613	.620
	Within Groups	94.737	11	8.612		
	Total	110.588	14			
Alkalinity	Between Groups	1424.583	3	474.861	1.300	.323
	Within Groups	4018.750	11	365.341		
	Total	5443.333	14			
Acidity	Between Groups	1037.083	3	345.694	2.546	.110
	Within Groups	1493.750	11	135.795		
	Total	2530.833	14			
CO ₂	Between Groups	565.554	3	188.518	1.505	.268
	Within Groups	1378.190	11	125.290		
	Total	1943.744	14			
Hardness	Between Groups	.093	3	.031	.382	.768
	Within Groups	.896	11	.081		
	Total	.989	14			
Sodium	Between Groups	936759.533	3	312253.178	.606	.625
	Within Groups	5668587.800	11	515326.164		
	Total	6605347.333	14			
Potassium	Between Groups	633.111	3	211.037	.255	.857
	Within Groups	9119.118	11	829.011		
	Total	9752.229	14			
DO	Between Groups	5.120	3	1.707	2.302	.134
	Within Groups	8.155	11	.741		
	Total	13.275	14			
BOD	Between Groups	.737	3	.246	.963	.444
	Within Groups	2.807	11	.255		
	Total	3.545	14			

Summary and conclusion

Water is an invaluable resource essential for life, sustainable growth, and development, yet it is increasingly threatened by anthropogenic pressures such as rapid urbanization, unsustainable development practices, and improper waste disposal. The present study to evaluate water quality across 15 sampling stations, focusing on parameters including temperature, pH, conductivity, total dissolved solids (TDS), salinity, hardness, acidity, alkalinity, carbon dioxide, sodium, potassium, dissolved oxygen (DO), biochemical oxygen demand (BOD), and most probable number (MPN). Results indicated that temperature (27–30°C, mean 28.2°C), pH (7.17–8.45, mean 7.76), conductivity (2.34–11.8 µs/cm, mean 7.45 µs/cm), salinity (1.18–9.56 ppt, mean 4.08 ppt), and TDS (1.70–9.56 ppm, mean 5.99 ppm) were within or close to acceptable limits, while alkalinity (60–120 mg/L, mean 89.33 mg/L) and acidity (7.5–27.5 mg/L, mean 17.66 mg/L) reflected variations in buffering capacity. Carbon dioxide (4.4–39.6 mg/L, mean 18.48 mg/L), hardness (0.8–1.8 mg/L, mean 1.42 mg/L), sodium (3.35–20.45 mg/L, mean 1383.66 mg/L), and potassium (8.94–16.07 mg/L, mean 131.47 mg/L) showed considerable spatial variation, influenced by seawater intrusion and anthropogenic inputs. Dissolved oxygen was generally low (1.1–4.2 mg/L, mean 2.47 mg/L), while BOD ranged between 0.2–1.78 mg/L (mean 1.02 mg/L), suggesting moderate organic pollution. Alarmingly, MPN values were consistently high, with several sites exceeding 1600, indicating significant fecal contamination. Overall, while most physicochemical parameters remain within permissible limits, the elevated microbial load and high sodium concentrations render the estuary water unsuitable for domestic use, highlighting the urgent need for sustainable management and pollution control measures.

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